

doi:10.5281/zenodo.14728260

The Role Of Diversity Management Strategies In Bolstering Task Cohesion In Telecommunication Firms In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Task cohesion is integral to the performance and well-being and performance of the organisation. Related challenges of such within the organisation, could stem unit and collaboration and that way, pose as a setback to the effectiveness or success of the organisation. This study thus examined the role of diversity management strategies comprising recruitment, training and participative leadership in task cohesion within telecommunication firms in Nigeria. The accessible population was 4 GSM telecommunication in Rivers State, with data generated from 36 referents using the questionnaire instrument. Results showed significant and positive relationships between the dimensions of diversity management strategies and task cohesion, leading to the conclusion that diversity management strategies, are integral to the organisations capacity to effectively harmonise the values and interests of its various groups. It was recommended that leadership actions are taken in line with strengthening recruitment, training and participative practices in the organisation in creating a more integrated and collaborative work environment.

Keywords: Task cohesion, recruitment, people management, training, participative leadership, diversity management

INTRODUCTION

Organisations have in recent years, become more dynamic. Such dynamism owes to the emerging conditions of globalisation and the increasing integration of global and diverse talent within the workplace (Mollel et al, 2015;). Ogbonna and Jerry (2018) argued that the related differences linked to a diverse workforce can be problematic to the organisation. Studies (Cary et al, 2018; Lauring, 2013) identify the lack of cohesion and effective workforce integration as significantly challenging for organisations, especially in the management of teams and the accomplishment of group or organisational goals. Poor task cohesion as Barsade and Gibson (2012) argued, can create loopholes in the organisation's communication and operational framework, further complicating its effectiveness. Research (Hu & Liden, 2015; Shin, 2014; Barsade & Gibson, 2012) justifies the need for task cohesion, affirming to its imperatives for the health and performance of organisations. Bradley et al (2012) posited that individual personalities, experiences and perceptions vary substantially. Such variance, impacts their interpretation of roles and tasks in the workplace and that way, could pose challenging for collaborations.

Task cohesion, according to Barsade and Gibson (2012) describes the extent to which functions or responsibilities are harmoniously carried out and are also integrated effectively to drive support. Where

members are able to work and experience connection with others, they are more engaged and, in most cases, demonstrate resilience. This is because, conditions of collaboration and cohesion in the workplace, foster knowledge and skill sharing; driving the overall competence of the organisation (Barsade & Gibson, 2012). This corroborates Bradley et al (2012) observation that cohesion when it comes to responsibilities and tasks, is a reflection of the depth or quality of relationships or connection between workers in the organisation. Emerging organisational realities, linked to globalisation, are considered as aggravating some of the relationship gaps, workplace conflicts and collaboration issues in most organisations. Related studies (Ogbonna & Jerry, 2018) identify these concerns as characterising most multinational organisations. Most of these, operating within the context of African countries such as Nigeria; are further exposed to the complexities associated with various multiethnic groups even at the local level.

Ozbiigin (2005) noted that such levels of diversity, at the international and at the local level, requires a more detailed and strategic approach to people management. Such that not only builds on the differences reflected in national backgrounds, but such that also integrates concerns of underpinning multiethnic issues as well. However, considerations of such diversity levels and their impact on task cohesion have scarcely been addressed, especially within the context of multinational firms in Nigeria. According to Ozbiigin (2005) effective diversity management strategies, should hinge on creating a more visibly connected and integrated workforce, drawing on knowledge or understanding about overarching national ties, and existing disparities that may exist or prevail between local groups and ethnicities yet captured within the context of the organisation. Thus, this research expands knowledge as it delves into the role of diversity management strategies in bolstering task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Nigeria. To This end, the objectives of the study are to:

- i. Ascertain the relationship between recruitment and task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Rivers State
- ii. Determine the relationship between training and task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Rivers State
- iii. Investigate the relationship between participative leadership and task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Rivers State

Theoretical Framework

Social Identity Theory

Employees within the organisation have perceptions of self, their placement, and relationship with other members of the organisation. These perceptions shape the disposition of the employee toward their work and the organisation as a whole. This condition is best illustrated using the social identity theory (Green & Youn, 2019). Proposed Tajfel and Turner in the mid-80s (Osborne & Mohamad, 2017; Green & Young, 2019), the social identity theory identifies the individual's perception of self as hinged on a number of factors, all integrated in advancing a picture or representation of the workers interpretation of self (Lauring, 2013). To understand workers openness to working with and collaborating with others, it is imperative to draw on the workers identification or sense of placement with groups they share or don't share with others (Green & Youn, 2019).

This theory enriches knowledge on the nature of the role of group identification in the behaviour, choices and actions of employees toward members of other groups. According to Flory et al (2021), not only do categories and groupings within the organisation influence the employee's behaviour and attitude toward others from other groupings, they invariably impact the extent of internal integration and as such the extent of task cohesion in the workplace. The social identity theory serves as a suitable theoretical premise in expanding the significance of diversity, such as reflected at the national and ethnic level, and the impact of such on the task cohesion of the organisation. Cary et al (2020) affirmed to the imperatives of harmonising group values and interests with those of the organisation, as a basis for strengthening workers identification with the organisation.

Diversity Management Strategies

Diversity describes the broad range of differences that exist between people and which forms or can be considered as the basis for their classifications or groupings (Jenssens & Steyaert, 2019). Within the organisation or workplace, diversity can be considered as the underlying characteristics that shape and determine the various collectives, categories and groups in the organisation (Lu et al, 2015). Diversity management strategies thus, refers to the approaches and methods in which organisations harmonize or balance the concerns and interests of various groups in the organisation, in ways that assure of improved outcomes of cooperation and intergroup disposition. Research (Besic & Hirt, 2016; Amaliyah, 2015; Dhupper, 2015; Amir et al, 2019; Akinnusi et al, 2017) points to some way through which organisations can develop cohesive and more integrated workplaces. These include the use of strategic recruitment criteria targeted at balancing group distributions and presence within the workplace, programs that drive cross-categorisation in terms of shared roles and responsibilities, as well as policies that emphasize participation and employee inclusion (Besic & Hirt, 2016; Dhupper, 2015).

However, the approach to managing and strategically harmonising diversity based on nationalities and ethnic differences, is such that as argued by Besic and Hirt (2016) and Dhupper (2015), should focus more on fusing of identity. That is important as it emphasizes the significance tenets of the social identity theory, especially the tenet on self-categorisation. Dhupper (2015) posited that through the development of programs that target group integration through the training designed to tackle language barriers, the adoption of organisational values and ideology, and the acceptance of others, Foma (2014) affirmed that such strategies anchor on promoting the values and demonstrating its dominance over those of the various groups in the organisation. Ensuring that the values of all parties and groups are aligned with those of the organisation. Diversity management strategies as Dhupper (2015) posited, should seek to bridge the gaps in terms of opportunities and resource allocation as well. This follows the need for strategies that address trust issues and transparency in the organisation; particularly through group inclusion and participative decision-making.

Task Cohesion

Task cohesion is reflected in the extent of agreement and harmony between groups and units in the organisation, as demonstrated through the fusion of functions and responsibilities (Shin, 2014). Hu and Liden (2015) asserted that cohesion is integral to coherence, as responsibilities are more integrated and communication flow is more consistent and effective. These conditions are not only linked to the structure and arrangement of work, are underpinned by the nature of the relationship between workers. Hu and Liden (2015) stated that in line with the changes necessitated by globalisation, such as the increased mix of the organisation's workforce, it is important that steps are taken to also update and upgrade people management approaches in mitigating the negative effects or impact of high diversity on the organisations well-being. Barsade and Gibson (2012) argued that just like the emerging and evolving dynamics of the environment, people management professionals must also realign their skills and competence in view of the conditions and frameworks that are increasingly shaping the workplace, such as in the case of group disparities or diversity.

Diversity Management Strategies and Task Cohesion

Bridging the differences between groups, and the harmonisation of values and interests in the organisation is no easy task (Abugu & Jerry, 2018). This borders on not only investing in programs and the modification of existing structures in most cases, but it is also hinged on the development trust, and the demonstration of leadership non-bias in its administration and distribution of resources or opportunities. Imran et al (2021) argued that despite the changing dynamics of work and the emergence of formats such as remote and hybrid work, people management activities and focus have not changed, however its tools and methods have been adjusted to align with emerging technologies and infrastructure. This also applies to concerns of global talent and the management of such. Related workplace multilingual technologies, and software facilitated by Artificial Intelligence (AI) currently mark people management approaches in bridging communication gaps between nationals and even local ethnic groups (Besic & Hirt, 2016; Handayani, 2017).

Similarly, organisations are steadily engaged in training programs that are designed to equip workers with the required knowledge and skills in effectively relating and collaborating with co-workers from other nationalities or ethnic groups (Ogunsanwo et al, 2020)). Flory et al (2021) posited that when it comes to workplace interpersonal relations, it is imperative that details such as religion, societal values and even cultural beliefs. These factors condition the behaviour of the individual and can influence their openness to other groups within the organisation. Diversity management strategies, as Arsel et al (2021) noted, must offer solutions to diversity problems or gaps that identify with the actual issues or basis of such differences. While strategies linked to job rotation, work rearrangement and others are also relevant, when it comes to national and ethnic concerns, it is imperatives that emphasis is placed more integration (Buengler et al, 2018). Hence, such should emphasis more on recruitment, training, and participative leadership practices. Thus, the following hypotheses are put forward:

HO₁: Recruitment significantly correlates with task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Rivers State

HO₂: Training significantly correlates with task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Rivers State

HO₃: Participative leadership significantly correlates with task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Rivers State

METHODOLOGY

The quantitative methodology is adopted in this research. This is in line with the study's underpinning positivism philosophy. Likewise, a correlational research design was adopted as the overall plan for the study. An accessible population of four telecommunication firms were adopted as the population for the study from which 28 supervisory staff were selected as units of measurement for the study. Selected telecommunication firms were based the criterion of their registration as Global Systems for Mobile (GSM) telecommunication firms. The data collection instrument was the questionnaire and it was administered to the main branches of the telecommunication firms in Rivers State. Instrumentation for the constructs of diversity management strategies and task cohesion are based on the previous research. Measurement for the instrument was also based on a 5-point Likert type scale, ranked from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree, with 3 = undecided.

DATA FINDINGS

Univariate data analysis

The result for the univariate distribution for this study is presented in the table 1

Table 1: Univariate distribution for the study

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Training	36	4.0714	.90898	-2.067	.393	2.778	.768
Recruitment	36	4.0595	.92731	-1.755	.393	1.563	.768
Participation	36	4.1786	.82411	-2.044	.393	3.678	.768
Task cohesion	36	4.0595	.98228	-2.019	.393	2.631	.768
Valid N (listwise)	36						

Source: Survey data (2024)

Illustrated on the table 1 is the result for the analysis for the distribution for the variables of the study. The distribution offers a summary position on the variables and their manifestations within the context of the telecommunication firms. The results indicate average positions which demonstrate participants agreement and affirmation to evidence of diversity management strategies (training, recruitment, participation and task cohesion) and task cohesion. Mean distributions and summaries for variables indicate substantial evidence of these variables within the target organisations.

Bivariate data analysis

The result for the test for the hypotheses of the study is presented in the table 2

Table 2: Test for the hypotheses of the study

		Task cohesion	Training	Recruitment	Participation
Task cohesion	Pearson Correlation	1	.956**	.899**	.649**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000
	N	36	36	36	36
Training	Pearson Correlation	.956**	1	.915**	.717**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000
	N	36	36	36	36
Recruitment	Pearson Correlation	.899**	.915**	1	.648**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000
	N	36	36	36	36
Participation	Pearson Correlation	.649**	.717**	.648**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	
	N	36	36	36	36

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey data (2024)

Based on the result illustrated on table 2. All related hypothetical statements are accepted. The results affirm to the significance of training to task cohesion (R = 0.956 and P = 0.000), recruitment to task cohesion (R = 0.899 and P = 0.000) and participative leadership to task cohesion (R = 0.649 and P = 0.000). The evidence demonstrates the significance of diversity management strategies to advancing task cohesion within the telecommunication firms. The results serve as a pointer to the imperatives of diversity management strategies in enabling a more harmonious and collaborative work environment. Thus, this research finds as follows:

4. Recruitment significantly correlates with task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Rivers State
5. Training significantly correlates with task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Rivers State
6. Participative leadership significantly correlates with task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Rivers State

Figure 1: The scatter diagram for task cohesion and diversity management strategies. The correlation for diversity management strategies and task cohesion is also reflected in the figure 1 of the study. The evidence further demonstrates a graphical relationship between the variables that is positive, affirming to the position of diversity management strategies as a predictor of the outcomes of task cohesion in the telecommunication companies.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

Diversity management strategies are demonstrated in this research to be significant and as such imperative to improved outcomes of task cohesion. Through the effective application of training, recruitment and participative leadership strategies, telecommunication firms can harness the potentials of group collaboration and a more harmonised work environment. The evidence presented in this research affirms to the importance of developing integrative structures and systems that are supportive and ensure the merging of group interests. The findings also reiterate the observation of previous scholars (Cary et al, 2020; Dhupper, 2015; Foma, 2014), through its reveal of the positive role of leadership as a crucial factor in the extent of group cooperation, trust and improved levels of altruism within the organisation. Similarly, following the evidence generated, one could argue that where strategies involve increased involvement in problem solving, there is a higher chance or tendency success and for shared responsibility for outcomes.

The evidence generated, further echo and by that, validate the tenets of the social identity theory, more especially on the basis of particular dimensions such as training and participative leadership (Green & Young, 2019). These are particular in their approach to not only equipping workers with the required skillset and knowledge for effectively engaging members of other groups, but also with the necessary framework through which they are able to voice their concerns and find meaningful placement within the context of the organisation. This position resonates with the views of scholars (Ogbonna & Jerry, 2018; Rohwerder, 2017) on the significance of integrative systems that support employee participation and the influence of that on the workers sense of placement, membership and belongingness in the organisation. Creating the enabling environment for levels of integration, must however have its parameters and framework for control and the specification of boundaries (Dhupper, 2015; Besic & Hirt, 2016).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The relationship between diversity management strategies and task cohesion, is one which as shown is positive, implying that related increases or improvements to diversity management activities or actions such as recruitment, training and participative leadership, would most likely contribute to similar increases or improvements in the outcome of task cohesion in the telecommunication firms. This illustrates the need for structures and policies within these organisations that not only emphasize and support these approaches to addressing related challenges of task cohesion, but also the need for consistency in such actions for long-term benefits. Thus, in conclusion, this study furthers the view that diversity management strategies are important and can substantially drive the task cohesion in telecommunication firms in Nigeria. It is therefore recommended as follows:

- i. The leadership of telecommunication firms in Nigeria, utilise criteria-based recruitment in balancing and addressing diversity gaps expressed in their workplaces; focusing on creating a more diverse and empowered workforce where particular groups do not feel out of place or marginalised.
- ii. The management of telecommunication firms in Nigeria, should focus on contextualising their training programs, ensuring a more detailed and tailored approach toward diversity management; such that builds on informing, equipping and aligning the values and concerns of its workforce with its diversity management goals and interests
- iii. The leadership of telecommunication firms in Nigeria, can address related trust issues or concerns of bias and favouritism through their involvement of employees in either direct or indirect representation (depending on which is suitable), and that way, increasing the level of belongingness, transparency and shared responsibility within the organisation.

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